

STUDENT-CENTERED EDUCATION OF SECOND-LANGUAGE
LEARNING

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Abstract: *The main focus of this article is on “student –centered learning” which claims to be one of the effective tools in the learning process. In this regard, the given research centers on the impact of adopting student-centered education in language acquisition. It is based on facilitating effective learning, which implies strong interaction between the learner and the teacher.*

Key Words: self-teaching, self-correction, cross-cultural, motivation.

INTRODUCTION.

Knowledge of one foreign language is not a sufficient criterion for the professional development of a university graduate and does not satisfy the needs of modern society, which is characterized by the constant expansion of international contacts in the sphere of economy, politics, and science.

Thus, it becomes necessary to teach future specialists to more than one foreign language, which makes it possible to continuously perfect the languages which have been taught and in the future to learn new foreign languages by self-teaching and self-correction. All this calls for the need to optimize the learning process because of the increasing demands on the level of professional competencies of university students.

MAIN PART.

We begin with presenting the pedagogical concept of Russian scholars G.V. Elizarova, V.V. Saphonova, V.P. Furmanova et al. that currently the basic goal of learning foreign languages is the creation of the multicultural identity. It is in accordance with P. Gilroy`s view that “we live in a world where identity matters. It matters both as a concept and as a contested fact of contemporary world”.

The former goal of learning foreign languages was to develop skills, which are particularly necessary for communication in educational situations and producing correct speech patterns.

Today higher education teachers have to face the challenge of developing their student`s multicultural or multilingual competence as a complex ability for culturally sensitive activity in cross-cultural communication.

Learning one more foreign language helps to create and develop multicultural identity of students. It is obvious that the more languages and cultures the students learn, the more tolerant and empathic towards representatives from other cultures they become. If they want to understand the culture, they need to acquire its language. Linguistically competent speakers can talk, express their feelings and share their opinions with others. As von Humboldt and Sapir argued, “to speak a given language means to embrace a given vision of reality, because languages differ not just in signs and phonemes but in worldviews”.

Describing the structure of student-centered learning we suggest that it differs from other kinds of developing education as it is aimed at creating subjective awareness but not training cognitive abilities. Highly-developed subjective awareness can have the following features:

- perceiving reality as man`s world;
- self-analysis, reflection, self-esteem, value about yourself;
- ability to cooperation, work in a team;
- values-based approach to exploring the world.

Student-centered learning is not aimed at moulding a personality with specified properties, but creates sufficient conditions for a full manifestation of student`s personal traits, accordingly, it develops personal functions of the educational process which predetermine making up of a personality, required by contemporary society. V.V. Serikov identifies the following personal functions: motivation, mediation, collisio, reflection, orientation, creativity, self-realization.

Student-centered learning – the function of motivation, because motivation characterizes the attitude of man to reality and is associated with a strong need for knowledge. The motive is a need or desire behind the actions of a person.

Psychologists believe that demands and motives are closely interrelated but the latter should not be only understood as person`s needs.

They highlight that needs are basic but not the only ones and not the number one motive for activity. Clearly, beliefs, feelings and interests can also serve as motives for activity, but only in case each of them becomes a need.

British researchers D. Nanan and J. Brindley suggest taking into account two factors in order to choose the right tasks. These factors are divided into those related to students and those related to the kind of tasks.

The factors related to students are the following:

- to what extent an task causes and supports student`s motivation. The same task can cause enthusiasm in some students or complete rejection from others;
- whether student`s skills allow him/her to do the task. Obviously, definite academic skills can influence the success in implementation of some kinds of tasks;

– how much information students can perceive per unit of time. In fact, the speed of learning is different. So it is really important to divide educational material in such a way that is suitable for each student;

– how good student`s speaking skills are. What level of language knowledge can be expected from this or that student according to the teacher`s assessment;

– if a student needs any specific linguistic-cultural competence for doing exercises. Can this knowledge be expected from each student?

– how deep language knowledge and skills of students are. What language knowledge is required for doing this task?

–how confident in his/her self-belief and competence a student is.

CONCLUSION.

Our thesis has been carried out and we conclude that moving towards student-centered education leads to greater success for students and increased job satisfaction for teachers.

It is the aim of the paper to inspire more higher education teachers to use a student centered approach as their teaching method. Studentcentered education in teaching a second foreign language can solve the issues caused by differences among students, can take into consideration a few factors which are based on the knowledge of each student`s subjective experience.

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